

DIMENSION OF IDENTITY DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF ACADEMIC BEHAVIOR OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine which domain of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of student. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in one District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of school year 2021-2022. Research instruments on dimension of identity development and management of academic behavior of student were used as source of data. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the level dimension of identity development is high, the level of management of academic behavior of student is high, there is significance on the relationship between dimension of identity development and management of academic behavior of student, and domain of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of student is Exploration in Breadth.

Keywords: dimension of identity development, management of academic behavior of student, educational management.

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of students in their academic undertaking is greatly dependent on the way they manage their academic behavior. Students who are good at handling their academic activities will most likely succeed. On the other hand, students who show disinterest to their educational responsibility will certainly lag behind with other students in the class. Hence, it is important that students must give their full attention in their lesson in order to meet the demands of the academic requirement in their grade level (Mim, Islam, & Kumar, 2018).

The necessity to sustain the interest of the student to their academic accountability is as important as their mastery of the competency standards of their level. In order to help students cope with the demands of their curriculum, it is helpful that they have a great deal of dimension of identity development. This will help them become academically driven. Likewise, this will help them increase their focus on achieving their goals to succeed (Duan, Guan & Bu, 2018).

Students have issues on their academic behavior as manifested in their tendencies to disregard the submission of the requirements of their subject. These students care less about what mark they get in their subjects and are disinterested to comply with their tasks even when they have been assisted with their submission. These students do not see the relevance why they study and they just continue to ignore the lessons in their subjects (Yao, Lian, Cao, Wu & Zhou, 2019).

In the local context, there are students who do not have focus on their tasks and teachers noted that these students do not see the value of learning. They do are disengaged and they avoid interaction with their teachers. More so, these students submit modules with items unanswered and they are fine with it. (Potgieter, 2015).

The problem-situations mentioned are the experiences of the students on their academic behavior. The need to address the problem will ensure greater learning opportunities for the students. Hence, the researcher is prompted to conduct this study to address the knowledge gap in terms of finding relevant evidence in the local context regarding dimension of identity development and management of academic behavior of students as the researcher has rarely come across with the same study on the same topic in the local setting.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to find out which domain of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of dimension of identity development in terms of:
 - 1.1. Commitment making;
 - 1.2. Exploration in breadth;
 - 1.3. Identification with commitment, and
 - 1.4. Exploration in depth.
2. To ascertain the level of management of academic behavior of students in terms of:
 - 2.1 Mastery self-talk;
 - 2.2 Relevance enhancement;
 - 2.3 Situational interest enhancement;
 - 2.4 Relative ability self-talk;
 - 2.5 Extrinsic self-talk, and
 - 2.6 Environmental structuring.
3. To determine the significant relationship between dimension of identity development and management of academic behavior of student.
4. To determine which domain of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of students.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis will be treated at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between dimension of identity development and management of academic behavior of students.
2. No domains of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of students.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of students.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of students.

Pearson-r. This was used to determine the relationship between dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of students.

Regression. This was used to determine which domains of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of students.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Dimension of Identity Development

Presented in Table 1 is the level of *Dimension of Identity Development* with the overall mean of 3.77 with a descriptive equivalent of *high* indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes manifested. The overall mean was the results obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which is appended in this study. Among the enumerated indicators, *Identification with Commitment* obtained the highest mean score of 3.98 or high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows:

Table 1. Level of Dimension of Identity Development

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Commitment Making	0.84	3.63	High
Exploration in Breadth	0.68	3.85	High
Identification with Commitment	0.46	3.98	High
Exploration in Depth	0.55	3.64	High
Overall	0.64	3.77	High

My plans for the future match with my true interests and values, My future plans give me self-confidence, Because of my future plans, I feel certain about myself, I sense that the direction I want to take in my life will really suit me, and I am sure that my plans for the future are the right ones for me.

The indicator *Exploration in Breadth* obtained the highest mean of 3.85 with a descriptive rating of high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I think actively about different directions I might take in my life, I think about different things I might do in the future, and I am considering a number of different lifestyles that might suit me.

Exploration in Depth obtained a mean score of 3.64 or high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I think about the future plans I already made, I talk with other people about my plans for the future, and I think about whether the aims I already have for life really suit me.

The indicator *Commitment Making* obtained a mean score of 3.63 or high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I have decided on the direction I am going to follow in my life, I have plans for what I am going to do in the future, I know which direction I am going to follow in my life, I have an image about what I am going to do in the future, and I have made a choice on what I am going to do with my life.

Level of Management of Academic Behavior of Students

Presented in Table 2 is the level of *Management of Academic Behavior of Students*. Computations revealed an overall mean score of 3.94 or *high*, indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes manifested. The overall mean was the results obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which is appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, *Environmental Structuring* obtained a mean score of 4.46 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I try to study at a time when I can be more focused, I change my surroundings so that it is easy to concentrate on the work, I make sure I have as few distractions as possible, and I try to get rid of any distractions that are around me.

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Table II. Level of Management of Academic Behavior of Students

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Mastery Self-talk	0.48	4.25	Very High
Relevance Enhancement	0.68	4.21	Very High
Situational Interest Enhancement	0.46	3.14	High
Relative Ability Self-talk	0.75	3.25	High
Extrinsic Self-talk	0.63	4.34	Very High
Environmental Structuring	0.88	4.46	Very High
Overall	0.83	3.94	High

Extrinsic Self-talk obtained a mean score of 4.34 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I remind myself about how important it is to get good grades, I tell myself that I need to keep studying to do well in class, I convince myself to keep working by thinking about getting good grades, and I remind myself how important it is to do well on the tests and assignments.

Mastery Self-talk obtained a mean score of 4.25 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I tell myself that I should keep working just to learn as much as I can, I persuade myself to keep at it just to see how much I can learn, I challenge myself to complete the work and learn as much as possible, and I convince myself to work hard just for the sake of learning.

Relevance Enhancement obtained a mean score of 4.21 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I tell myself that it is important to learn the material because I will need it later in life, I try to connect the material with something I like doing or find interesting, I think up situations where it would be helpful for me to know the material or skills, and I try to make the material seem more useful by relating it to what I want to do in my life.

Relative Ability Self-talk obtained a mean score of 3.25 or high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I think about doing better than other students in my class, I tell myself that I should work at least as hard as other students, I keep telling myself that I want to do better than others in my class, and I make myself work harder by comparing what I'm doing to what other students are doing.

The indicator *Situational Interest Enhancement* obtained a mean score of 3.21 or high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: I make studying more enjoyable by turning it into a game, I try to make a game out of learning the material or completing the assignment, I try to get myself to see how doing the work can be fun, and I make doing the work enjoyable by focusing on something about it that is fun.

Significance on the relationship between Dimension of Identity Development and Management of Academic Behavior of Students

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between the variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed r- value of 0.389 with a probability value of 0.02 which is significant at 0.05 level.

Table III. Significance of the Relationship between Dimension of Identity Development and Management of Academic Behavior of Students

Dimension of Identity Development	Management of Academic Behavior of Students		
	R	p-value	Remarks
Commitment Making	.388	.001	Significant
Exploration in Breadth	.126	.010	Significant
Identification with Commitment	.269	.001	Significant
Exploration in Depth	.308	.000	Significant
Overall	.389	.002	Significant

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Doing an in-depth analysis, it could be gleaned that the indicators of *Dimension of Identity Development* and *Management of Academic Behavior of Students* revealed a computed r-values ranging from .126 to .388 with probability values of 0.01 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. The significant relationship between the two variables is an indication that the increase in the level of *Dimension of Identity Development* led to the increase in *Management of Academic Behavior of Students*.

Significance of the Influence of the Domain of Dimension of Identity Development on Management of Academic Behavior of Students

Presented in Table 4 is the regression analysis showing the predictive ability of *Dimension of Identity Development* on *Management of Academic Behavior of Students*.

Table IV. Regression Analysis Showing the Extent of the Influence of Predictor Variables on Management of Academic Behavior of Students

<i>Management of Academic Behavior of Students</i>				
	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	1.7293	0.6283	1.92	0.000
Commitment Making	-0.02683	0.02681	0.08	0.428
Exploration in Breadth	0.82931	0.08392	1.88	0.006
Identification with Commitment	0.08256	0.06195	0.06	0.624
Exploration in Depth	0.02498	0.06278	0.04	0.821
R	0.254			
R²	0.925			
F	43.26			
p	0.000			

The analysis shows that when *Dimension of Identity Development* was regressed on *Management of Academic Behavior of Students*, it generated an F-value of 43.26 with 0.01. The value of this regression is 43.26 with 0.01. It can be stated that *Attitudes Towards the Use of Multimedia* influenced *Management of Academic Behavior of Students*. Among the indicators of *Dimension of Identity Development* only one gave significant influence on *Management of Academic Behavior of Students*, which is *Exploration in Breadth*, $t=1.88$, $P=0.006$.

V. CONCLUSION

With considerations on the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The level of dimension of identity development is high, the level of management of academic behavior of student is high, there is significance on the relationship between dimension of identity development and management of academic behavior of student, and domain of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of student is *Exploration in Breadth*.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study revealed that the level of dimension of identity development is high. The researcher recommends that the District where the study is conducted in Schools Division Office of Davao Occidental may conduct training that will help improve the aspects of Commitment Making.

Meanwhile, the study revealed a high level of management of academic behavior of student. The researcher recommends that the district office may provide Learning Action Cell among the teachers on the topic Situational Interest Enhancement.

The study found a significant relationship between dimension of identity development and management of academic behavior of student. The researcher therefore recommends that the District Office may consider the provision of trainings or activities relative to the variables under study to help the school heads and teachers enhance on the indicators which are among the lowest in the indicators of the variables under study.

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The study found that the domains of domain of dimension of identity development best influences management of academic behavior of student is Exploration in Breadth. The researcher recommends that school heads may provide sessions in Learning Action Cell among teachers for improvement.

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